

EXCHANGE RATE STABILITY AS A CATALYST FOR FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN NIGERIA

¹Okereke Ike Godslove, ²Adetunji Rebecca Oluwakanyinsola, ³Wodu Ebitimi Victory Peremoboere, ⁴Ajayi Mojolaoluwa, ⁵Yusuf-Towoba Sultan Abayomi and ⁶Olutayo Daniella Tanitoluwa

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of exchange rate stability on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows in Nigeria using annual data from 1987-2024. The data were sourced from World Development Indicators (WDI). Exchange rate, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and Inflation were used as the independent variables, while FDI was the dependent variable. Unit root test was conducted using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron statistics, and the result indicated a mixed order of integration. Bound test result indicated that there is a significant long-run relationship between the variables under study. Autoregressive Distributive Lag Model (ARDL) was employed to examine both short run and long run relationships among the variables. The findings revealed that the exchange rate had a negative but statistically insignificant effect on FDI, GDP had a positive and statistically significant effect on FDI, and inflation had a positive and statistically insignificant effect on FDI. The error correction term, which is negative and statistically significant, indicates that 71% of short run disequilibrium is corrected annually. The study concludes that while exchange rate stability is important, GDP is more effective in attracting FDI into Nigeria. It recommends policies that promote sustainable economic growth, exchange rate stability, price control and structural reforms to improve the investment condition in Nigeria.

1. Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is an investment from a resident entity in one country into a business or corporation in another country with the intention of establishing or maintaining a lasting interest and control. In Nigeria, FDI has contributed to economic growth through increase in employment opportunities, development of human capital, and technology transfer. However, despite Nigeria's large market size and abundant resources,

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Department of Economics, Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State

FDI inflows have remained unstable and have declined in recent years (UNCTAD, 2023; CBN, 2023). In developing countries like Nigeria, foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows are seen as a critical catalyst for economic growth and the most important factor influencing FDI decision is the stability of the host country's macroeconomic environment (Njoku et al. 2025).

Exchange rate stability is a key factor influencing foreign investors' decisions. A stable exchange rates will reduce any uncertainty and improve confidence in future returns, which encourages long-term foreign investment in an economy. In Nigeria, frequent exchange rate fluctuation, continuous depreciation of the naira, and changes in exchange rate regimes has increased uncertainty in business environment for foreign investors which erodes confidence and discourages capital commitment in the long term (Okafor and Eze, 2024). In addition, macroeconomic factors such as GDP and inflation also affect FDI inflows. GDP counts all the output generated within the borders of a country. It shows the size, growth, capacity and progress of an economy. Inflation is the rate of increase in prices over a given period of time, it serves as an indicator of price instability and macroeconomic risk. Although Nigeria's GDP reflects strong market potential, high inflation and economic instability have increased production costs and reduced real returns on investment (IMF, 2023). This factors, poses significant risks to maintaining a stable and attractive investment environment (David Babatunde Ayoola, 2024). The relationship between exchange rate stability and FDI is explained by the Balance of Payments Theory, which is the record of a nation's financial transactions with the rest of the world in a fiscal year, usually one year (Lagoarde-Segat,2023; Adewale et al. 2025). It focuses on the role of capital flows in correcting external imbalances and stabilizing the exchange rate. Similarly, the Portfolio Balance Theory suggests that international investors allocate capital based on expected returns and associated risks, with exchange rate stability being a key determinant of portfolio choice. In this framework, stable exchange rates, sustained economic growth, and controlled inflation are expected to enhance foreign direct investment inflows into Nigeria.

Despite several monetary and fiscal policy reforms aimed at improving Nigeria's investment environment, foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows into the country have remained unstable and low. A major challenge is exchange rate instability, shown by frequent depreciation of the naira and uncertainty in the foreign exchange market (CBN, 2023). In 2015 exchange rate moved from ₦192.4/\$ to ₦358.8/\$ in 2020, inflation also increased from 9.01% in 2015 to 13.2% in 2020 causing GDP to drop from 2.65% in 2015 to -6.36% in 2020 and FDI inflows to decline from 0.62% in 2015 to 0.39% in 2020. This shows that high exchange rate volatility, high inflation rate, and unstable GDP often lead to a decline in foreign capital inflows (World Bank, 2015; World Bank, 2020). Sometimes GDP can increase, as in 2021, when the exchange rate moved from ₦401.1/\$ to ₦425.9/\$ in 2022, inflation increased from 16.9% in 2021 to 18.8% in 2022, but GDP grew from 1.1% in 2021 to 4.3% in 2022, and FDI still declined from 0.54% in 2021 to -0.02%. Although Nigeria has a high GDP, it has not led to consistent FDI inflows, which means that market size alone is not enough in an unstable economic environment.

Existing studies have examined factors influencing FDI in Nigeria, but limited attention has been given to the combined role of exchange rate stability, inflation, and GDP using recent data. This study broadly examined how exchange rate stability affects foreign direct investment inflows in Nigeria. This study will contribute to the existing literature and understanding of how exchange rate stability affects foreign direct investment inflows. It will provide policymakers and investors with crucial insights to formulate effective policies that promote investor confidence.

2. Literature Review

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a long term investment made by foreign individuals or multinational companies in the productive sectors of another country with the aim of establishing control or significant

influence. Recent studies describe FDI as a major source of external finance that support employment opportunities, development of human capital, technology transfer and overall economic growth. In Nigeria, FDI has contributed to the development of key sectors such as oil and gas, telecommunications and manufacturing. However, recent evidence shows that FDI inflows into the country have been unstable due to macroeconomic challenges (Ukamaka and Awogbemi, 2026; Okereke, 2025).

Exchange Rate

Exchange rate stability is one of the most important macroeconomic factors influencing foreign investment decisions in Nigeria. Exchange rate represent the value at which one currency can be exchanged for another and plays a crucial role in determining a country`s international competitiveness (Ukamaka and Awogbemi, 2026). When the exchange rate is stable, investors feel more confident because they can predict their future returns. But when the exchange rate is unstable too often, it creates uncertainty and increases risk which discourages foreign investors. (Ukamaka and Awogbemi, 2026) also stated that a predictable exchange rate lowers the risk associated with cross border transactions, encouraging business to expand and investors to commit capital. While persistent unpredictability makes it difficult for investors and business to plan which affect foreign direct investment negatively.

Theoretical Review

Balance of Payment Theory

The Balance of Payment (BOP) represents a detailed financial record of a country`s economic transactions dealings with other countries, over a specific period of time, usually a year. This transactions include exchange in goods and services, income flows, financial transfer and flow of capital (Hassan et al. 2025). The BOP serves as a key indicator of a country`s external economic performance and is essential for evaluating the sustainability of its exchange rate and its capacity to meet international obligations (Sultani and Faisal, 2022). The balance of payment consist of the capital and financial account, which tracks capital movements including foreign direct investment and portfolio investment, and current account which manages investment and transfer income in addition to commodities and service trade. The capital account is strengthened by these capital inflows, which can enhance the balance of payments (Oghenetjiri and Ezi, 2025).

Exchange rate is an important determinant of Balance of payment position in a country. When it is used well it can serve as a nominal anchor for price stability. When the demand for a local currency decreases for a certain exchange amount; we could fine deficiency in its balance of payments because increase export and discourages import. In the same way, if the demand for a nation`s currency increased for a given rate of return, we would see surplus in their balance of payment because it weaken export and encourages import (Irmiya et al. 2023). Exchange rate fluctuation can affect the current account by altering the competitiveness of import and export, as well as the capital account be affecting the attitude of foreign investors. Exchange rate instability discourages foreign investment and weakens capital inflows. Since FDI constitutes a major component of financial account of balance of payments, exchange rate instability can indirectly weaken the BOP position through reduced foreign investment inflows (Oghenetjiri and Ezi, 2025).

Empirical review

Several studies have examined the relationship between exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria, producing mixed but complementary findings. Akinwale et al. (2024) found that a stable exchange rate encourages foreign investors, with volatility discouraging investment decisions. Their FMOLS regression results suggest that macroeconomic stability is crucial for attracting FDI. Similarly, Adamson et al. (2025), using GARCH and multiple regression models, reported that exchange rate volatility has a positive but

statistically insignificant effect on FDI, while GDP and treasury bill rates negatively influence inflows. This highlights the broader role of macroeconomic instability in shaping investment outcomes.

Other scholars emphasize the dual short-run and long-run effects of exchange rate volatility. Oladipo (2025) showed that volatility negatively affects FDI in the short run but positively in the long run, suggesting that investors may adapt over time. Okereke (2025), however, found a consistently negative impact of exchange rate fluctuations on FDI, concluding that continuous depreciation of the naira discourages inflows. Uthman (2025) added nuance by noting that while FDI is positively related to naira depreciation, volatility increases risk and reduces inflows. Fasina (2022) also observed a positive relationship between FDI and exchange rate fluctuation, but trade openness and inflation weakened investment.

Extending the discussion to economic growth, Ukamaka and Awogemi (2026) revealed that exchange rate volatility negatively affects both FDI inflows and GDP, underscoring the importance of a stable regime for sustainable development. International perspectives reinforce these findings: Chikwira and Jahed (2024) showed that exchange rate stability supports GDP growth, while McCloud et al. (2024) found that FDI can influence exchange rates but not vice versa, with government stability moderating outcomes. Alwadeai et al. (2025) further demonstrated that sanctions increase volatility, but FDI helps stabilize exchange rates, highlighting the protective role of foreign investment against external shocks.

Research Gap

From the empirical studies reviewed, some gaps were identified in terms of variables and methodology. Based on variables, many studies used different macroeconomics indicators to explain FDI inflows. Fasina (2022) examined exchange rate together with inflation and trade openness, Adamson et al. (2025) examined exchange rate alongside treasury bill rate and Akinwale et al. (2024) also used various variables in explaining FDI inflows. Despite all this, few studies combined exchange rate, GDP and inflation together. This creates a gap because foreign investors consider market size, price stability and exchange rate before investing. Based on methodology, most studies like Fasina (2022), Akinwale et al. (2024), Okereke (2025) and Ukamaka and Awogbemi (2026) used econometric models such as OLS, ARDL and VECM. While these methods show relationships between variables, many of them focused on direct or linear effects and did not examine exchange rate stability as a catalyst that can drive foreign investment inflows. Also some used old data periods that do not reflect recent reforms. Therefore, this study fills the gap by examining exchange rate stability as a catalyst for FDI inflows in Nigeria alongside GDP and inflation using recent data from 1987 to 2024.

3. Methodology

The study uses annual time series data from 1987-2024. The data were collected from WDI. The variables used in the study are FDI and Exchange rate. Other independent variables are GDP and Inflation. Unit root test was conducted using Autoregressive Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron Statistics. Result from these tests integrated in order 1(0) and 1(1). The method used is Autoregressive Distributive Lag Model (ARDL).

The functional form of the model is specified as follows:

$$FDI = f (EXR, GDPGR, INF) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

In its econometric form, the model is expressed as:

$$FDIt = \beta_0 + \beta_1EXRt + \beta_2GDPt + \beta_3INFt + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Therefore, equation 3.2 was re-specified as the following error correction model:

$$\Delta FDI_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_{1t} \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta FDI_{t-1} + \alpha_{2i} \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta \ln EXR_{t-1} + \alpha_{3t} \sum_{i=t}^p \Delta GDPGR + \alpha_{5t} \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta INF_{t-1} + \beta_1 EXR_{t-1} + \beta_2 GDPGR + \beta_3 INF + \epsilon_t$$

(3.3)

Where:

FDI_t = Foreign Direct Investment at time tEXR_t = Exchange Rate at time tGDP_t = Gross Domestic Product at time tINF_t = Inflation Rate at time t β_0 = Intercept $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Slope or coefficients of the respective explanatory variables ε = Error term which captures all other variables not included in the model (2).

t = Time period

 Δ denoted change in the short-run changes α_j (1, 2, 3, 4) are the short-run parameters β_j (1, 2, 3, 4) are the long-run parameters**Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics**

	FDI	EXR	GDP	INF
Mean	1.316931	106.1233	4.086649	20.28852
Median	1.177898	99.77896	4.212993	13.12650
Maximum	4.282088	273.0019	15.32916	72.83550
Minimum	-0.028873	49.77484	-6.368898	5.388008
Std. Dev.	0.963771	46.58501	4.033922	17.09509
Skewness	0.787930	1.972301	0.112297	1.663670
Kurtosis	3.526160	7.131436	3.945625	4.610748
Jarque-Bera	4.370284	51.66201	1.495695	21.63736
Probability	0.112462	0.000000	0.473384	0.000020
Sum	50.04339	4032.687	155.2926	770.9639
Sum Sq. Dev.	34.36761	80296.02	602.0834	10812.96
Observations	38	38	38	38

Source: Author's Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

From the Table 4.1, there is 38 observations for each variable. The statistical attributes of the variables, including mean, median, maximum, minimum, among others, along with the distributional patterns of the variables, are also explained by the results. With regard to the Jarque-Bera estimates and their corresponding probability values, it was shown that while the variables (FDI and GDP) exhibited normal distributions with probability values of $0.112462 > 0.05$ and $0.473384 > 0.05$ respectively, the remaining variables (EXR and INF) did not comply to normality, as evidenced by their Jarque-Bera statistical probability values of $0.000000 < 0.05$ and $0.000020 < 0.05$.

Table 4.2 Correlation Matrix

	FDI	EXR	GDP	INF
FDI	1.000000			
EXR	-0.529106	1.000000		
GDP	0.233777	-0.186929	1.000000	
INF	0.134427	-0.092070	-0.306737	1.000000

Source: Author's Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

Table 4.3 Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
EXR	9.13E-06	6.730856	1.063359
GDP	0.001332	2.390604	1.163848
INF	7.22E-05	2.771435	1.132783
C	0.229285	12.64317	NA

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

Result from table 4.2 and 4.3 show that there is no author correlation between the independent variables as the correlation coefficient result is less than 0.8 and VIF values are all less than 10. This implies that there is no problem of multicollinearity in the model.

Table 4.4 The Augmented Dickey Fuller Test Result

ADF									
AT LEVELS					AT FIRST DIFFERENCE				
INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT		INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT	
Variables	ADF statistics	5% Critical Value	ADF statistics	5% Critical Value	Variables	ADF statistics	5% Critical Value	ADF statistics	5% Critical Value
FDI	-3.584	-2.943	-2.964	-3.540	FDI	-9.310	-2.946	-9.242	-3.540
EXR	-2.689	-2.943	-2.607	-3.537	EXR	-5.546	-2.946	-5.489	-3.540
GDP	-3.964	-2.943	-3.964	-3.537	GDP				
INF	-3.592	-2.946	-3.149	-3.537	INF	-6.222	-2.946	-6.215	-3.540

Source: Author’s computation (2026) using E- Views 12

Table 4.5 Phillips Perron Test Result

PHILLIPS PERRON									
AT LEVELS					AT FIRST DIFFERENCE				
INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT		INTERCEPT			TREND AND INTERCEPT	
Variables	PHP statistics	5% Critical Value	PHP statistics	5% Critical Value	Variables	PHP statistics	5% Critical Value	PHP Statistics	5% Critical Value
FDI	-3.637	-2.943	-4.150	-3.537	FDI				
EXR	-2.833	-2.943	-2.759	-3.537	EXR	-5.514	-2.946	5.452	-3.540
GDP	-3.870	-2.943	-3.875	-3.537	GDP				
INF	-2.930	-2.943	-3.282	-3.537	INF	-7.569	-2.946	-8.780	-3.540

Source: Author’s computation (2026) using E-Views 12

According to table 4.4 and 4.5, there is a mixed order of integration as some variables are stationary at levels while some are stationary at first difference. This justifies the use of ARDL in estimating the parameters in the model.

Table 4.6 Lag Length Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-461.1209	NA	4101623.	26.57834	26.75609	26.63970
1	-421.9522	67.14649*	1099946.*	25.25441*	26.14318*	25.56121*
2	-411.1830	15.99983	1542689.	25.55332	27.15310	26.10556
3	-397.4072	17.31818	1939827.	25.68041	27.99121	26.47810

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

The result depicts that different lag criteria has their respective lag length. The most commonly use lag criteria is Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). From the result depicted, AIC chose lag 1 as the best lag length for the model but for this study lag 2 is being used.

Table 4.7 ARDL Bound Test Result

Test-Statistics	Value	K
F-Statistics	4.719584	3
CRITICAL VALUE BOUNDS		
Significance	1(0)Bound	1(1)Bound
10%	2.37	3.2
5%	2.79	3.67
2.5%	3.15	4.08
1%	3.65	4.66

The result in Table 4.7 shows that F-Statistics value is greater than the upper bound at 5% significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant long-run relationship among the variables.

Table 4.8 Regression Output

PANEL A : SHORT RUN MODEL				
VARIABLE	COEFFICIENT	STANDARD ERROR	T-STATISTICS	PROBABILITY
FDI(-1)*	-0.713794	0.160376	-4.450765	0.0001
EXR**	-0.003280	0.003403	-0.963909	0.3433
D(INF)	0.004161	0.011938	0.348566	0.7300
D(GDP)	-0.016599	0.039413	-0.421144	0.6769
C	0.881358	0.515002	1.711370	0.0981
CointEq(-1)*	-0.713794	0.137449	-5.1933173	0.0000
PANEL B : LONG RUN MODEL				
EXR	-0.004595	0.004439	-1.035087	0.3095
GDP	0.129611	0.055994	2.314746	0.0282
INF	0.002226	0.014530	0.153222	0.8793
C	1.234751	0.660762	1.868677	0.0722
Diagnostic Test for ARDL Estimations				
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test				
F-Statistics	0.645278	Prob. F (2,26)	0.5327	
Obs*R-squared	1.702422	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.4269	
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey				

F-Statistics	1.338143	Prob. F (7,28)	0.2698
Obs*R-squared	9.024329	Prob. Chi-Square (7)	0.2509
Scaled explained SS	2.650570	Prob. Chi-Square (7)	0.9153
Jarque-Bera Probability			
Statistics	2.477852	Probability	0.289695

Author`s computation (2026) using E-Views 12

Result from table 4.8 shows that in the short run, the error correction term is negative and significant (-0.7138, $p = 0.0000$), meaning that about 71% of short run disequilibrium in FDI is corrected each year, confirming the existence of a stable long run relationship. EXR has a negative but insignificant effect on FDI with a coefficient of -0.0033 ($p = 0.3433$). GDP has a negative but insignificant effect on foreign direct investment (FDI) with a coefficient of -0.0166 ($p = 0.6769$). Inflation also has a positive but insignificant effect short run effect on FDI with a coefficient of 0.0042 ($p = 0.7300$). This shows that short term changes in economic growth do not influence FDI inflows immediately.

In the long run, the exchange rate has a negative but insignificant effect on FDI with a coefficient of -0.0046 ($p = 0.3095$), suggesting that exchange rate movement do not strongly determine FDI inflows in Nigeria. GDP has a positive and statistically significant effect on FDI with a coefficient of 0.1296 ($p = 0.0282$). This means that market size matters, when Nigeria`s economy grows foreign are attracted. Inflation has a positive but insignificant long run effect on FDI with a coefficient of 0.0022 ($p = 0.8793$), showing that inflation does not play a major role in determining long term FDI inflows.

Diagnostic tests show the model is reliable. There is no serial correlation ($p = 0.5327$), no heteroskedasticity ($p = 0.2698$) and errors are normally distributed (Jarque-Bera $p = 0.2897$).

Stability tests are essential for examining various aspects, including the validity of the model utilized in the research. The CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares plots stay within the 5% significance bounds throughout the period (1987- 2024). This means the ARDL model is stable and there is no structural break in the relationship between FDI, EXR, GDP and INF. Despite major economic shocks in Nigeria like the 2008 global financial crisis, 2016 recession, COVID-19 shock and 2023 fuel subsidy removal and so on.

4. Discussion And Conclusion

This study examines exchange rate stability as a catalyst for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows in Nigeria from 1987 to 2024 using ARDL. The results show that there is long run relationship between FDI, exchange rate, GDP and inflation. This supports the Balance of Payment theory, which explains that exchange rate movements influence capital inflows and the country's external position. The findings reveal that GDP has a positive and significant effect on FDI in the long run. This means economic growth strongly attracts foreign investors because it increases market size and profit opportunities.

The exchange rate has a negative but insignificant relationship with FDI. Although not statistically strong, the negative sign means that persistent depreciation of the naira may discourage investors. This agrees with Okereke (2025), who found that exchange rate volatility reduces FDI inflows. Inflation has a positive but insignificant effect on FDI in both the short run and long run. Which means that a controlled inflation rate may not immediately discourage investors, but maintaining price stability remains important for overall economic performance. In the short run, the variables do not significantly influence FDI. This means foreign investors focus more on long-term economic performance rather than temporary macroeconomic changes. The speed of adjustment indicates that Nigeria's economy corrects shocks quickly, which is a positive signal. The study therefore concludes that exchange rate stability, though important in every economy, does not serve as a catalyst for foreign direct investment inflows in Nigeria; rather, GDP is the main determinant of foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

Policy Implications for Nigeria

1. The Central Bank of Nigeria should focus on exchange rate stability and implement a transparent framework that reduces volatility. Stability build investors' confidence.

2. The government should boost GDP growth through infrastructure, power supply and industrial development in order to attract investors.
3. Inflation targeting policies should be strengthened to maintain price stability.
4. Policies that improve investor protection and political stability will enhance FDI inflows.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

This study used annual data which may not capture short-term fluctuation accurately. Quarterly data provide deeper insights. This study also focused on only three macroeconomic variables influencing FDI (Exchange Rate, GDP, and Inflation). Future studies can include other variables such as political stability, interest rate, and trade openness. Researchers may also use quarterly data or nonlinear models to test the threshold effects, which provide deeper analysis. Researchers can also compare Nigeria with other African countries. In conclusion, exchange rate stability supports foreign investment, but economic growth remains the strongest driver of FDI in Nigeria.

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